

Reduction of Potassium Permanganate by Malonic Acid Part II. Influence of Different Electrolytes on the Reaction Rate

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The effect of different acids and salts on the kinetics of the reduction of potassium permanganate by malonic acid has been studied. The reaction is catalysed by HCl and H_2SO_4 . Sodium acetate has a retarding influence at low concentrations, but at higher concentrations the reaction is catalysed.

Bafna *et al.*¹ observed that the reaction between malonic acid and iodine was accelerated by HCl and H_2SO_4 . Srivastava and Ghosh² found a specific inhibitory effect of halide ions on the reaction between potassium persulphate and oxalic acid, whereas $FeCl_3$ catalysed the reaction with a maximum effect. Effect of H^+ and OH^- ions on the reduction of potassium permanganate has been studied by Gupta and Ghosh³ and by Wiberg and Stewart⁴.

In view of the above, it was considered of interest to extend the study of the effect of HCl, H_2SO_4 , KCl, K_2SO_4 , and sodium acetate on the reduction of potassium permanganate by malonic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were of extra pure quality and the solutions were prepared in fresh double distilled water.

Standard solutions of malonic acid, KCl, K_2SO_4 , and sodium acetate were prepared by direct weighing. A standard solution of potassium permanganate was always prepared, just before the start of the reaction, by filtering it through a sintered glass crucible and standardising it with 0.1N oxalic acid solution.

The amount of unreduced potassium permanganate, at different intervals of time, was estimated iodometrically. The pH of the reaction mixture was determined by a Cambridge pH-meter.

The amount of potassium permanganate reduced was plotted against time and from these curves, the time for half-reduction of potassium permanganate was determined.

1. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1952, 11B, 376.
2. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1956, 205, 332.
3. *Ibid.*, 1958, 209, 310.
4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 1786.

TABLE I

Effect of HCl, H₂SO₄, KCl, and K₂SO₄ on the reaction rate.[H₂C(COOH)₂]₀ = 0.05*M*. [KMnO₄]₀ = 0.002*M*. Temp. = 30°.

Electrolyte added.	Conc. of the added electrolyte.	Time for half-reduction of KMnO ₄ .
Nil	..	58 min.
HCl	0.005 <i>N</i>	48
H ₂ SO ₄	0.005	50
KCl	0.005	60
K ₂ SO ₄	0.005	62

DISCUSSION

From Table I it is observed that both HCl and H₂SO₄ catalyse the reaction. HCl, being stronger, catalyses the reaction to a greater extent. KCl and K₂SO₄ exert an inhibiting influence on this reaction. This may be due to specific inhibiting influence of the Cl⁻ and SO₄²⁻ ions. Further, the inhibition caused by SO₄²⁻ ions appears to be greater than the Cl⁻ ions.

Effect of Sodium Acetate.—The kinetics of the reaction between malonic acid and potassium permanganate was studied in presence of different concentrations of sodium acetate. It was found that the overall nature of the reaction was not altered by the addition of sodium acetate. It is interesting to note that at lower concentrations of sodium acetate, the reaction is retarded, but at high concentrations it is accelerated.

The time for half-reduction of potassium permanganate in presence of different concentrations of sodium acetate was obtained from the amount of KMnO₄ reduced—time curves and it was plotted against the concentration of sodium acetate to ascertain the extent to which sodium acetate affected the reaction rate. The results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

[H₂C(COOH)₂]₀ = 0.04*M*. [KMnO₄]₀ = 0.002*M*. Temp. = 30°.

Conc. of Na-acetate (moles/litre).	pH of the mixture.	Time for half- reduction of KMnO ₄ .
..	2.26	67 min.
0.010	2.58	106
0.025	3.18	142
0.050	4.20	114
0.100	4.86	73
0.200	5.23	45

Table II shows that between pH 2.26 and 3.18, sodium acetate inhibits the reaction and above this pH, it exerts a catalytic influence (Fig. 2). The optimum concentration of sodium acetate, at which maximum retardation takes place, is 0.025 *M*.

Effect of the Initial Concentration of Malonic Acid on the Optimum Concentration of Sodium Acetate.—The effect on the optimum concentration of sodium acetate, at which maximum retardation took place, was studied by varying the initial concentration of malonic acid and keeping the concentration of potassium permanganate same in the reaction mixture. The pH of the reaction mixture at the optimum concentration of sodium

acetate was also noted and the optimum concentration was calculated from Fig. 1 (a, b, c, d). The results are recorded in Table III.

FIG. 1

In curves a—d, the conc. of $\text{H}_2\text{C}(\text{COOH})_2$ represents respectively 0.04, 0.05, 0.06, and 0.08M.

FIG. 2

$\text{H}_2\text{C}(\text{COOH})_2 = 0.04M$, $\text{KMnO}_4 = 0.002M$. Temp = 30° .

It appears from Table III that the optimum concentration of sodium acetate reaches a definite pH, i.e. 3.1 to 3.18, independent of the initial concentration of malonic acid. The optimum concentration of the former increases as the initial concentration of the latter is increased (column 2, Table III). This observed increase in the optimum concentration of sodium acetate can be explained on the basis of pH observation; by increasing the initial concentration of malonic acid, the pH of the reaction mixture is decreased in order to attain the same pH (3.1—3.18), as required at the optimum point, more sodium acetate will be required resulting in the higher concentration of it.

TABLE III

$[\text{KMnO}_4]_0 = 0.002M$. Temp. = 30° .

Initial conc. of malonic acid.	Optimum conc. of Na-acetate (from Fig. 1).	pH of the mixture.
0.04M	0.025M	3.18
0.05	0.030	3.15
0.06	0.035	3.12
0.08	0.045	3.10

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